

Effect of dielectric constant of medium on protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid

G. Nageswara Rao* and V. L. S. N. Murthy

School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India

E-mail : gollapalli@yahoo.com Fax : 91-891-2755547

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The effect of dielectric constant on the protonation-deprotonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid was studied by varying urea or DMF in the ranges 0–36.83%, w/w or 0–60%, v/v, respectively. The protonation constants were evaluated using MINIQUAD 75, from alkalimetric titration data obtained pH metrically at 303 K temperature and 0.16 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength. The linear variation of protonation constants with inverse of dielectric constant of the medium suggests that electrostatic forces are dominating in the equilibrium process.

L-Glutamine and succinic acid actively participate in acid-base equilibria especially in physiological pH conditions. L-Glutamine has three functional groups (amido, amino and carboxyl) but only two (amino and carboxyl) are protonated, whereas succinic acid has two carboxyl groups. Hence, an understanding of the protonation-deprotonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid is necessary in the investigation of the complex equilibria of these ligands. The protonation constants in acetonitrile-water¹ and ethylene glycol-water² mixtures were reported earlier. No such reports in urea-water and dimethyl formamide (DMF)-water media were available. The results of the investigations on the protonation constants of L-glutamine and succinic acid in urea-water and DMF-water mixtures are reported in this

communication.

Results and discussion

The computer program SCPHD³ prunes the alkalimetric titration data to eliminate the noise and calculates the step-wise protonation constants, which are given as initial protonation constants to the computer program MINIQUAD75⁴ for the final refinement. The best-fit models are chosen based on the statistical parameters produced by MINIQUAD75. The results are given in Table 1. The statistical parameters given in the tables were discussed earlier⁵. It can be inferred from these data that the stability constants vary linearly (and against 1/D) with urea or DMF content in the aqueous solution.

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of acido-basic equilibria

Urea % w/w	log β (SD)	log β (SD)	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R
In urea-water mixtures (ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³ ; temp. = 303 K) :								
L-Glutamine (pH range = 1.5 to 11.0)								
0	9.27 (1)	11.66 (2)	147	0.59	-0.43	3.84	31.77	0.016
05.80	9.15 (1)	11.50 (4)	96	0.20	0.15	3.09	10.08	0.014
11.52	8.64 (1)	10.44 (1)	92	0.47	0.10	2.72	13.74	0.021
20.31	8.20 (1)	9.90 (3)	122	0.75	0.18	1.98	30.10	0.022
29.64	7.93 (2)	9.29 (1)	87	0.25	0.58	3.17	8.16	0.014
36.83	7.76 (1)	9.29 (2)	101	0.68	1.98	8.09	38.55	0.025
Succinic acid (pH range = 3.0 to 7.0)								
0	5.43 (1)	9.46 (1)	88	0.21	-1.31	6.82	10.36	0.014
05.80	5.31 (1)	9.25 (6)	120	7.60	-2.87	6.30	62.67	0.017
11.52	4.90 (3)	8.47 (1)	99	0.18	-1.67	7.25	42.65	0.013
20.31	4.57 (2)	7.90 (6)	99	8.91	-0.71	3.45	29.56	0.009

Table-1 (contd.)

29.64	4.45 (4)	7.61 (1)	78	0.21	-0.95	4.32	13.64	0.016
36.83	4.25 (7)	7.34 (4)	83	8.25	-0.40	2.54	5.95	0.011

In DMF-water mixtures (ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³; temp. = 303 K):

DMF

%, v/v

L-Glutamine (pH range = 1.5 to 11.0)

0	9.27 (1)	11.66 (2)	147	0.59	-0.43	3.84	31.77	0.016
10	8.97 (7)	11.10 (4)	121	0.69	-0.30	2.99	35.02	0.014
20	8.95 (7)	11.37 (1)	126	0.94	-0.10	3.18	17.40	0.011
30	8.93 (4)	11.64 (4)	165	1.08	1.45	5.14	27.77	0.045
40	8.91 (2)	11.90 (2)	105	1.05	-1.00	4.04	9.05	0.031
50	8.87 (7)	12.43 (1)	87	1.22	-1.50	2.62	14.69	0.012
60	8.82 (4)	12.98 (2)	107	0.58	-0.17	3.20	41.93	0.023

Succinic acid (pH range = 3.0 to 7.0)

0	5.43 (1)	9.46 (1)	88	0.21	-1.31	6.82	10.36	0.014
10	5.56 (8)	9.66 (6)	87	0.71	-0.07	2.61	10.18	0.008
20	5.69 (3)	9.85 (4)	70	0.15	-3.64	4.39	10.32	0.006
30	5.82 (4)	10.06 (3)	63	0.18	-0.34	2.86	14.32	0.011
40	5.96 (3)	10.28 (4)	72	0.16	-0.38	2.59	8.56	0.014
50	6.20 (2)	10.68 (4)	60	0.56	0.73	3.24	18.13	0.014
60	6.48 (4)	11.12 (3)	59	0.17	0.47	2.52	43.76	0.012

$U_{\text{corr}} = UI(NP - m) \times 10^9$, where, U_{corr} = sum of squares of residuals corrected for degrees of freedom, U = sum of squares of residuals in all the concentrations, NP = number of experimental points and m = number of species.

The stability constant increases with $1/D$ inferring that the electrostatic forces⁶ are greatly influencing the protonation-deprotonation equilibria. These equilibria were depicted in our earlier publication¹.

The protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are shown in eqs. (1), (2) and (3), (4), respectively.

The less charged or neutral species are more stabilized in the medium of less dielectric constant. Thus, with decreased dielectric constant (or increased $1/D$ value), the protonation constants of the equilibria shown in eqs. (2) and (4) are more increased than those for the equilibria given in eqs. (1) and (3).

Distribution plots generated using the protonation constants given in Tables 1 and 2 show the formation of LH_2^+ , LH and L^- in the case of L-glutamine and LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} in the case of succinic acid. Typical distribution plots in urea-water medium are given in Fig. 1. The zwitterionic

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of (A) succinic acid and (a) L-glutamine, in 5.8%, w/w urea-water mixture.

form (LH) of L-glutamine is present to an extent of 90% in the pH range 4.0–8.0. In the case of succinic acid, the concentrations of LH_2 and LH^- have decreased with increase in urea content and the maximum concentration of each species is shifted to lower pH. These observations indicate the destabilization of the species in the presence of urea.

Experimental

Solutions (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of L-glutamine and succinic acid (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. The

probable errors in the concentrations of the stock solutions were determined by the computer program COSWT⁷. The concentrations of mineral acid (HCl) and alkali were determined by the Gran plot method⁸. Urea (A.R., B.D.H.) was crystallized twice from distilled water and dried at 60° for 2 h. Stock solution of urea was stored frozen and it was never allowed to stand at RT continuously for more than 24 h⁹. The DMF was distilled under reduced pressure.

A Systronic-335 model pH meter (0.01 readability) was used to carry out alkalimetric titrations. The calibration and equilibration of glass electrode and determination of correction factor were discussed in our earlier publication¹⁰. The titrations were carried out in media containing varying amounts of urea (0.0–36.83%, w/w) or DMF (0.0–60%, v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with NaCl at 303.0 ± 0.1 K temperature. The titrand consisted of mineral acid and the ligand in a total volume of 50 cm³. The titrations were performed by successive addition of 0.1 cm³ NaOH (*ca.* 0.4 mol dm⁻³) to the titrand.

The evaluation of stability constants and refinement of the models were performed using MINIQUAD75, as given

elsewhere¹¹.

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